

Light Pollution and Orbital Debris Observations

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Abstract: Optical observation of orbital debris is hindered not only by light pollution from the ground but also by interference from other orbital debris objects passing through the observation frame. According to NASA classification, orbital debris is composed of non-operational spacecraft, derelict launch vehicle stages-rocket bodies, mission-related debris and fragmentation debris. This work will present the successful optical observations of SL-16 R/B (COSPAR ID: 1999-039B, SATCAT: 25861) and SL-16 R/B (COSPAR ID: 1995-058B, SATCAT: 23705) rocket bodies in McKnight Top 50 2019 and 2022 list, Resurs DK-1 (COSPAR ID: 2006-021A, SATCAT: 29228) non-operational spacecraft, GAOFEN 11 (COSPAR ID: 2018-063A, SATCAT: 43585) operational civilian remote sensing satellite and Cosmos 1892 (SATCAT: 18421, COSPAR ID: 1987-088A) non-operational spacecraft. The orbital debris observations were made from non-permanent observatory located at Novi Sad metropolitan area, Serbia and quantified the impact of various light pollution sources. The light pollution dome that mainly impacts the observing site is visible to the east towards the Novi Sad urban settlement, but this only has a large impact on orbital debris observations with overpass elevation angles below 30 degrees. The rural suburban areas are under constant impact of the development of large storage halls-warehouses and truck parking areas, which during the night are completely enlightened and contribute largely to the localized light pollution. Other sources of light pollution on our orbital debris observations are Starlink satellite overpass tracks and light from the phases of the Moon. Our future work will include observations from Accra, Ghana and Bangalore, India.

Keywords: dark sky park; digital camera; light pollution; airglow.

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